

Geographical distribution and bionomics of the Zygaenids of Hungary with illustrations (Lepidoptera: Zygaenidae)

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Abstract. The study is a comprehensive synthesis of information on 26 known Hungarian species of Zygaenids. This work is used as a guide for the distribution maps of the Zygaenidae species. It is the second summary work on the geographical distribution of Hungarian species. The preparatory work for this study was started 40 years ago with planned collecting activities, revisions of museum, institutional and private collections, and writing of faunistic monographs on Zygaenids from several geographic regions. Colour photographs of the species are included.

Keywords. Zygaenidae, bionomy, distribution maps, Hungary.

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Introduction

More than 1000 species of Zygaenidae are known world-wide, of which about 120 are recorded in the Western Palearctic. This number may be significantly modified by genetic studies. The Zygaenidae family is represented in Hungary by 26 species in 4 genera. Zygaenidae are diurnal moths with a very variable habitus, biology and ecology.

According to Nahirnić (2019), *Zygaena diaphana* Staudinger, 1887 is bona species. According to this author, both species inhabit different types of habitats on the Balkan Peninsula. Moreover, Nahirnić also found genitalic differences not only between these two species but also between other taxa of the *Zygaena minos*-complex. Unfortunately, at the moment, such studies are not available for the Carpathian Basin. This is important because in the old Hungarian literature (Gozmány 1963) the *diaphana* species was identified from Hungary. Later studies have not confirmed this (Fazekas 2002, 2009). Based on Nahirnić's concept, the entire species complex should be reviewed in Hungary. It is possible that the geographical distribution of *Z. diaphana* extends into the Carpathian Basin.

The first detailed book on Zygaenidae in Hungary was published in 2009 (Fazekas 2009), in which the history, zoogeography, and conservation aspects of Zygaenidae research was presented. The diagnosis, bionomics, Hungarian and Palearctic geographic distribution of all species were described, with illustration of habitus and genitalia. Over the last 12 years, the distribution data of species have changed significantly, and several new bionomic observations have modified our knowledge of the species.

With the help of the book, many Hungarian collectors started small or large-scale research, especially in lesser-known geographical areas, where very little information was available. The correct identification of the species collected, observed, and illustrated has been verified, so that they are authentic occurrences.

The identification of Procrinae species remains a problem for collectors. Therefore, data on Procrinae are only included for which voucher specimens have been provided. Their identity was confirmed by genital examination.

This paper summarises these studies and complements the book published in 2009. The expanded new maps published here show the current distribution patterns of the species.

Material and methods

The distribution maps are based on the division of the natural geographic landscape of Hungary (Marosi & Somogyi 1990, Dövényi 2010), into ecologically distinct large, medium and small landscapes. The names and geographical locations of these areas are shown in Figure 5, 6.

The author collected the data in an Excel database, which is continuously being expanded. The site data were mapped on to UTM GRID 10x10 km grid. For ease of reference, only the 50x50 km grid is shown. This mapping method has been used by the author for 30-40 years. The new expanded and revised maps are easily comparable with the maps of the previously published Hungarian book on Zygaenidae (Fazekas 2009).

Information on larval food plants is partly from personal observation, partly derived from the literature.

Genitalia dissections were done in accordance with Robinson (1976). Some of the genitalia were mounted in Euparal on slides; others are preserved in micro-vials filled with glycerol. Genital analysis of worn, damaged specimens of Procridinae was performed using the simple and rapid method of Wanke and Rajaei (2018).

The material examined is in the following collections: Bakonyi Természettudományi Múzeum (Zirc); Janus Pannonius Múzeum (Pécs); Jász Múzeum (Jászberény); Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum (Budapest); Mátra Múzeum (Gyöngyös); Pannon Intézet (Pécs); Ripp-Rónai Múzeum (Kaposvár); Savaria Múzeum (Szombathely).

Key to external morphology

Distribution and bionomics of species

Figure 1. Key to external morphology of the Procridini genera (wings form)

Figure 2. Key to external morphology of the *Theresimima ampellophaga* (2a) and *Rhagades pruni* (2b); antennal structures (apical) and wings form

Figure 3. Key to external morphology of the *Adscita statices* (3a) and *A. geryon* (3b) antennal structures (apical) and wings form

Figure 4. Key to external morphology of *Jordanita* genera antennal structures (apical) and wings form

Summary and list of names, with Hungarian names

The author has tried to correct the data existing in the old as well as in the recent literature for Hungary and to update the faunistic records in accordance with the recent achievements of taxonomy. For this reason, all available collections in Hungary have been checked and many taxa are critically examined to establish with certainty which is indeed present in Hungary.

A protected species: **PS**; Highly protected: **HP**; Value in Hungarian forints: Ft.

PS: *Adscita geryon*, *Jordanita graeca*, *Zygaena fausta*

HP: *Zygaena laeta*

After the Latin names I give the Hungarian names of the species.

Systematic part and nomenclature (Fazekas 2009, pp. 16–17).

Note: The species are numbered. In the text, species are numbered consecutively so that they are easy to find.

ZYGAENIDAE – Csüngőlepke-félék

Subfamilia PROCRIDINAE Boisduval, [1828] – fémlepkék (zöld csüngőlepkék)

Genus *Theresimima* Strand, 1917

1. *Th. ampellophaga* (Bayle-Barelle, 1808) – kormospille

Genus *Rhagades* Wallengren, 1863

Subgenus *Rhagades* Wallengren, 1863

2. *R. (Rh.) pruni* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – kökény fémlepke

Genus *Adscita* Retzius, 1783

Subgenus *Adscita* Retzius, 1783

3. *A. (A.) geryon* (Hübner, 1813) – Gerión fémlepkéje – PS (5 000 Ft)

4. *A. (A.) statices* (Linnaeus, 1758) – sóska fémlepke

Genus *Jordanita* Verity, 1946

Subgenus *Roccia* Alberti, 1854

5. *J. (R.) budensis* (Speyer & Speyer, 1858) – budai fémlepke

Subgenus *Tremewania* Efetov & Tarmann, 1999

6. *J. (T.) notata* (Zeller, 1847) – aranyzöld fémlepke

6a. *J. (T.)* sp. cf. *notata* (Zeller, 1847) – The taxonomic status is questionable.

Subgenus *Jordanita* Verity, 1946

7. *J. (J.) graeca* (Jordan, 1907) – görög fémlepke – PS (5 000 Ft)

8. *J. (J.) chloros* (Hübner, [1813]) – ércfényű fémlepke

10. *J. (J.) fazekasi* Efetov, 1998 – Fazekas fémlepkéje

Subgenus *Solaniterna* Efetov, 2004

11. *J. (S.) subsolana* (Staudinger, 1862) – balkáni fémlepke

Subfamilia ZYGAENINAE Latreille, 1809

Genus *Zygaena* Fabricius, 1775 – vörös csüngőlepkék

Subgenus *Mesembrynus* Hübner, [1819]

12. *Z. (M.) punctum* Ochsenheimer, 1808 – pettyes csüngőlepke

13. *Z. (M.) cynarae* (Esper, 1789) – pusztai csüngőlepke

14. *Z. (M.) laeta* (Hübner, 1790) – vörös csüngőlepke – HP (100 000 Ft)
 15. *Z. (M.) brizae* (Esper, 1800) – magyar csüngőlepke
 16. *Z. (M.) minos* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – levantei csüngőlepke
 ? *Z. (M.) [diaphana* Staudinger, 1887] – So far unproven, its occurrence is possible.
 17. *Z. (M.) purpuralis* (Brünnich, 1763) – bíborszínű csüngőlepke
 Subgenus *Agrumenia* Hübner, [1819]
 18. *Z. (A.) fausta* (Linnaeus, 1767) – koronafürt csüngőlepke – PS (10 000 Ft)
 19. *Z. (A.) carniolica* (Scopoli, 1763) – fehérgyűrűs csüngőlepke
 Subgenus *Zygaena* Fabricius, 1775
 20. *Z. (Z.) loti* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – réti csüngőlepke
 21. *Z. (Z.) osterodensis* Reiss, 1921 – ördög szem csüngőlepke
 22. *Z. (Z.) viciae* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) – somkóró csüngőlepke
 23. *Z. (Z.) ephialtes* (Linnaeus, 1767) – változékony csüngőlepke
 24. *Z. (Z.) angelicae* (Ochsenheimer, 1808) – vérpettyes csüngőlepke
 25. *Z. (Z.) filipendulae* (Linnaeus, 1767) – hatfoltos csüngőlepke
 26. *Z. (Z.) loniceriae* (Scheven, 1777) – here csüngőlepke

Map of the natural- and zoogeographical division of Hungary

Figure 5.

Symbols in the UTM maps (1–26)

- Recent breeding populations
- Known populations before 1960
- + Disappearance or possible extinction
- ? The occurrence is questionable or unproven. There are records in the literature, but specimens have disappeared.

Figure 6. Natural geography map of Hungary, by macroregions (1-6) and mesoregions (e.g. 1.1, 1.2, etc.). Hungarian names, designations. Ecological competences after Fazekas (2017)

1 Alföld

- 1.1 Duna menti síkság
- 1.2 Duna-Tisza közti síkság
- 1.3 Bácskai-síkság
- 1.4 Mezőföld
- 1.5 Dráva menti síkság
- 1.6 Felső-Tisza-vidék
- 1.7 Közép-Tisza-vidék
- 1.8 Alsó-Tisza-vidék
- 1.9 Észak-Alföldi-hordalékkúpság
- 1.10 Nyírség
- 1.11 Hajdúság
- 1.12 Berettyó-Körös-vidék
- 1.13 Körös-Maros köze

4 Dunántúli-dombság

- 4.1 Balaton-medence
- 4.2 Külső-Somogy
- 4.3 Belső-Somogy
- 4.4 Mecsek és Tolna-Baranyai-dombvidék
 - 4.41 Mecsek
 - 4.433 Villányi-hegység

2 Kisalföld

- 2.1 Győri-medence
- 2.2 Marcal-medence
- 2.3 Komárom-Esztergomi-síkság

3 Nyugat-magyarországi-peremvidék

- 3.1 Alpokalja
- 3.2 Sopron-Vasi-síkság
- 3.3 Kemeneshát
- 3.4 Zalai-dombság

5 Dunántúli-középhegység

- 5.1 Bakony-vidék
- 5.2 Vértes-Velencei-hegyvidék
- 5.3 Dunazug-hegyvidék

6 Észak-magyarországi-középhegység

- 6.1 Visegrádi-hegység
- 6.2 Börzsöny
- 6.3 Cserhát-vidék
- 6.4 Mátra-vidék
- 6.5 Bükk-vidék
- 6.6 Aggtelek-Rudabányai-hegyvidék
- 6.7 Tokaj-Zempléni-hegyvidék
- 6.8 Észak-magyarországi-medencék

Figure 7. UTM grid map of Hungary: 100x100 and 50x50 km divisions

Figure 8. Well and less researched geographic areas of Hungarian Zygaenidae species; well researched (red line), researched but knowledge is incomplete (green line). Information on unmarked areas is largely scarce.

1. *Theresimima ampellophaga* (Bayle-Barelle, 1808)

In Hungary, this species was a serious pest in grape plantations in the 19th Century. It has been observed in all famous Hungarian wine regions. It is most widespread west of the Danube: Villány Hills, Mecsek Mountains, and near Lake Balaton. There are very few records from vineyards in the lowlands. The larvae of *T. ampellophaga* cause damage in the spring by hollowing out the buds. In May, the young larvae feed on the underside of leaves; later, they chew irregular holes in the leaves. The loss of photosynthesizing area is frequently significant on the whole plant (Voigt et al. 2000).

Bionomy: flight period from late May to late July and second generation in August and September. Voigt et al. (2000) carried out pheromone trapping studies in two vineyards (Budakeszi, Kecskemét). According to the catches, the flight started after June 20, and specimens were caught in largest numbers between June 26 and July 3. The flight went on at decreasing intensity until the middle of July. More detailed studies are needed to establish the exact flight time. It is necessary to clarify whether the August generation observed in Hungary is permanent or occurs only in certain geographical areas and only in certain years.

2.

Note: In the text, the numbering of the figures is based on the number of species (1-26).

Rhagades (Rhagades) pruni ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Occurs primarily in Transdanubia and in the North Hungarian Mountains, sporadic and rare on the plain (e.g., Kiskunság, Nyírség). The size of the populations is not known because of the deficiency of records.

Bionomy: flight period from mid-June to mid-August. Polyphagous species, the larvae feed mainly on *Prunus spinosa*, but also on *Crataegus monogyna*, *Calluna vulgaris*, *Helianthemum nummularium*, *Rhamnus catharticus*, *Rosa canina*, *Quercus petraea* and *Qu. robur*. The larvae were observed in 2019 on *Quercus virginiana* in the Mecsek Mountains in southern Hungary. Habitat: grasslands with spontaneously colonising trees and shrubs, coniferous woodlands, continental deciduous rock thickets, thermophilous woodland fringes, open dry deciduous woodlands, fresh deciduous woodlands, slope steppes, closed rock grasslands, *Calluna* heaths.

2a

2b. Habitat in Mecsek Mountains (Mecsekjános)

3. *Adscita (Adscita) statices* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Widespread and locally common on hills and in medium-high mountains, mainly west of the Danube (Transdanubia/Dunántúl in Hungarian) and in the Northern Central Mountains. It is very local and rare in the lowlands. There are strong populations on the plain near the Drava River, near the Croatian border.

Bionomy: univoltine, flight period from mid-May to mid-August. Larva feeds on *Rumex acetosa*, *R. acetosella*, *R. conglomeratus*, *R. obtusifolius*, *R. scutatus*, *R. stenophyllus*. According to Gozmány (1963) the larvae live on *Globularia* spp.

Habitat: rich fens, eu- and mesotrophic meadows and tall herb communities, colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, secondary and degraded marshes, and grasslands.

Remarks: the area of preferred habitats is rapidly decreasing. Most threatened by agriculture and construction.

4. *Adscita (Adscita) geryon* (Hübner, [1813])

This species is protected in Hungary; its incorporeal value is 5 000 HUF. Very local and rare, and populations are very much reduced in its known localities: Mecsek Mountains., Somogy county, Budapest, and its neighbourhood. The most stable populations are in northern Hungary, in the Bükk Mountains, a national park. Gene flow is uncertain, the species is probably in regression. Continuously present in the Kiskunság National Park since 2000 (see arrow on the map): “Peszéradacsi-rétek” (Máté A. pers. comm.)

Bionomy: univoltine, in July. Larva feeds on *Geranium robertianum*, *G. lucidum*, *G. sanguineum*, *Erodium cicutarium*, *E. ciconium*, *Helianthemum canum* and *H. nummularium*.

Habitat: calcareous open rock grasslands, closed rock grasslands, rock steppes, slope steppes (e.g., in Transdanubian- and North Hungarian Mountains) and *Cynosurion* grasslands (in West Hungarian Borderland).

Remarks: the survival of populations is mainly a problem around large cities (e.g., Budapest, Pécs, etc.). In the mountains, there are many tourists and heavy trampling of vegetation. In grazing areas, the number of animals is high, the number of food plants is decreasing, and there are few sources of nectar for the imago. The construction of housing estates has accelerated, and preferred habitats are disappearing very rapidly.

5. *Jordanita (Roccia) budensis* (Speyer & Speyer, 1858)

The species was described from Hungary as "Ofen" (= Buda, later Budapest). The exact locus typicus is not known. Unfortunately, most of the habitats that have been found have been destroyed or are highly endangered.

Very disjunct distribution with isolated populations in North Hungarian Mountains and Transdanubian Mountains. Strikingly local and rare in the Great Hungarian Plain (e. g., Kiskunság). Was not seen for more than fifty years in the Mecsek Mountains (South Hungary). The species is threatened with extinction in the neighbourhood of the larger cities (e. g. Budapest). Unknown along the eastern and western borders.

Bionomy: univoltine, flight period from mid-May to mid-July. Larva feeds on *Achillea setacea*, *Carduus nutans*, *C. acanthoides*, *Centaurea solstitialis*, *C. triumfetti*, *C. diffusa*, *C. salnitana*, *C. scabiosa*, *Chrysanthemum vulgare* and *Matricaria recutita*.

Habitat: open sandy steppes, calcareous open rock grasslands, closed rock grasslands, rocky steppes, slope steppes.

Remarks: from a scientific and conservation point of view, it is quite surprising why the species is ignored by the official Hungarian conservation authorities. To date it is not listed as a protected species. This would be expected for any species described from Hungary. Conservation of the type of locality should be a priority and permanent monitoring surveys should be carried out in National Parks. There is also no explanation why it is not included in the Hungarian "Red Book". These omissions should be remedied as soon as possible.

6. *Jordanita (Tremewania) notata* (Zeller, 1847)

Very local and rare in Hungary, and absent from extensive geographical areas. The size of the populations is unknown. The species is threatened with extinction in the neighbourhood of the larger cities (e.g., Budapest, Pécs). The distance between the isolated populations is large, and the possibility of genetic regeneration is not ensured. There is a lack of so-called "steppingstones".

Bionomy: flight period from late May to early July. There is a late autumn specimen from Hungary: 1 ♂, Magyarszombatfa, 8–9. X. 1979, leg. light trap. According to Naumann et al. (1999) and Freina & Witt (2001), univoltine in most localities; May–July. However, in Spain on wing from end of March to middle of September with interruption in August (2 generations?). According to the new Hungarian data, it is possible that *J. (T.) notata* is bivoltine in the Pannon region. Larva feeds on *Centaurea scabiosa*, *C. jacea* and *C. salotina*.

Habitat: colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, closed rock grasslands, rock steppes, white oak scrub woodlands.

The forewing ground colour is very rarely copper

(6c) *Jordanita* sp. cf. *notata* (Zeller, 1847)

A single specimen was collected in an area of grassland in Western Hungary, with *Centaurea jacea*, *C. scabiosa* and *Carduus nutans*, *C. crispus*. The dominant plants in the biotope are species of *Festuca* and *Agrostis*.

Remarks: a photograph of the specimen and genitalia drawings were sent to K. A. Efetov (UA-Simferopol) and G. M. Tarmann (A-Innsbruck). According to their opinion, the specimen is perhaps an aberrant *J. (T.) notata*. This seems possible, but there are fundamental differences from that species. K. A. Efetov also supposed that short 8th sternite, structure of the juxta and pointed process of the sacculus indicate that the specimen could be a hybrid of *J. notata* and *J. globulariae*, both species feeding on *Centaurea*. There is no specimen like this described in the scientific literature. Examination of more material is necessary before this taxonomic problem can be solved (Fazekas & Efetov 2009a).

6f Landscape structure in the Magyarszombatfa settlement in Western Hungary

6e Magyarszombatfa
46.79679, 16.34882

7. *Jordanita (Jordanita) graeca* (Jordan, [1907])

This species is protected in Hungary; its incorporeal value is 5 000 HUF. Local and very rare on the hills and in the mountains of medium height. Has not been seen for more than fifty years in the Budapest neighbourhood. Unknown in the south. The Hungarian populations are a long distance from those in the Balkans. Gene flow is uncertain; the species may be in regression and endangered in Hungary. It should be protected in nature reserves and National Parks (Mátra Mountains, Bükk Mountains). There is a lack of proper research and a shortage of experts. Only a few lepidopterists can identify the species.

Bionomy: univoltine; flight period from mid-May to end June. Larva feeds on *Carduus hamulosus*, *Centaurea salonitana*, *Serratula radiata*, *Xeranthemum annuum*.

Habitat: dry open grasslands, closed loess and sand steppes, slope steppes, rocky steppes.

Remarks: A very valuable postglacial relict species of the Pannonian biogeographical region. It should be sought throughout the whole region. There is a lack of knowledge about the reasons for the isolation of populations in Northern Hungary.

7c The map is full of old data. Some sites are known to date back more than 100 years. All collected specimens are in the collections. Unfortunately, the habitats have been destroyed. Live population Bócsa-Bugac (2004-2009): UTM Grid CS86 (Observed and investigated: András Máté)

8. *Jordanita (Jordanita) chloros* (Hübner, [1813]) The species was still widespread in Hungary in the first half of the 20th Century. It has disappeared from many of its old sites and there are no new observations (see Fazekas 2009). Nowadays it is a very local and rare species in Hungary. During the last Century it has disappeared from many places: around Budapest, Central-Hungary. In the Kiskunság National Park it is still common in some years. Unknown from eastern regions (e.g., Tiszántúl). There are very few specimens in the Hungarian collections.

Bionomy: flight period in June, July, and August. Larva feeds on *Globularia punctata*, *Centaurea pannonica*, *C. jacea*, *C. triumfetti*, *C. scabiosa* and *C. micranthus*.

Habitat: meadows, pastures, thickets, bushy forests, rocky steppe meadows.

Antenna (© Efetov 2005)

9. *Jordanita (Jordanita) globulariae* (Hübner, 1793)

Widespread and frequent on the hills and in the mountains of medium height, local on the plains. Stable populations are found in protected areas and National Parks: Mecsek-Bakony-, Mátra-, Bükk and Zemplén Mountains.

Bionomy: univoltine; flight period from mid-May to mid-August. Larva feeds on *Globularia punctata*, *Plantago lanceolata*, *Centaurea jacea*, *C. scabiosa*. According to Gozmány (1963) the larvae also live on *Cirsium* spp.

Habitat: meadows, pastures, thickets, bushy forests, rocky steppe meadows.

Remarks: valva and aedeagus very variable (see Fazekas 2009; Fig. 29: c.); aedeagus with 5 cornuti (W Hungary, Vörs, gen. prep. Fazekas, No. 1156).

10. *Jordanita (Jordanita) fazekasi* Efetov, 1998

Local and very rare in south Hungary: Mecsek Mountains and Villányi Hills (locus typicus). A highly endangered species, its original habitats have been degraded or destroyed in recent decades. Most threatened by intensive quarrying, construction and trampling by tourists. There are many invasive plants everywhere, the original plant communities have been destroyed and replaced by *Pinus nigra*, *Robinia pseudoacacia* and *Ailanthus altissima*.

Differential diagnosis (according to Efetov 1998): *Jordanita (J.) fazekasi* is close to *J. (J.) vartianae* and *J. (J.) globulariae* but is characterized by the greater number of segments in the antenna (42–51); moreover, it has clear and constant differences in the genitalia. In *J. vartianae* (Fig. 8), which is endemic to Spain, the ventral side of the process arising from the sacculus is concave near the apex and the cornutus is curved at the base and similar in shape to that of a rose thorn. In *J. fazekasi*, the cornutus is straight, cone shaped. In *J. globulariae*, the aedeagus lacks a cornutus. Moreover, in *J. vartianae* and *J. globulariae* the pulvinus is not so large as in *J. fazekasi*. The sympatric occurrence of *J. fazekasi* and *J. globulariae* in Hungary (Fazekas 1980: 59, fig. 18e) confirms the opinion that *J. fazekasi* is a distinct species.

Biology: flight period early July. The larval foodplants are probably species of Asteraceae, as in other species of *Jordanita*.

Habitat: white oak scrub woodlands (*Inulo spiraeifolio-Quercetum pubescentis*) and calcareous open rock grasslands (*Sedo sopianae-Festucetum dalmaticae*).

11. *Jordanita (Solaniterna) subsolana* (Staudinger, 1862)

Regressive species which has disappeared from many localities. Local and very rare in Hungary. The most significant Hungarian population flourishes in the Northern mountain range of Hungary: Mátra Mountains, Bükk Mountains and Aggtelek Karst. In southern Hungary (e.g., in the Mecsek Mountains) the number of individuals is very low. The species disappears for years and is clearly in regression. In general, surprisingly few populations are known west of the Danube. The reasons for this have not been investigated.

Bionomy: flight period in June and July. There are no data from May and August. Larva feeds on *Echinops sphaerocephalus*, *E. ruthenticus*, *Carlina vulgaris*, *Cirsium vulgare*, *C. eriphorum* and *C. pannonicum*.

Habitat: colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, closed rock grasslands, rock steppes, white oak scrub woodlands.

Remarks: Unknown from eastern regions (e.g., Tiszántúl). There are studies in the eastern parts of the country, but researchers do not favour this group.

12. *Zygaena (Mesembrynus) punctum* Ochsenheimer, 1808

Zygaena punctum is known to be expanding its range in the Ponto-Mediterranean region, to the Pannonian basin as well as to Italy. It has been in recession in Hungary for the last 50 years and remains local in southwest Hungary, near the Croatian border. The author has recently found the species for the first time in Mecsek Mts. An image of *Z. punctum* was recorded on 30th June 2008 in the Mecsek Mountains (Pécsvárad). It was found in one locality only, but it was not abundant.

Bionomy: univoltine from end of May to end of July. The larvae feed on *Eryngium campestre*. According to Varga (1969) the larvae feed on *Centaurea* species. Known larval parasite: *Exoristala rvarum* and *Phryxe vulgaris* (Diptera: Tachinidae).

Habitat: A typical inhabitant of Pannonian steppe regions, occurring on dry, calcareous ground. Very local and rare.

12b. *Z. punctum* f. *isaszeghensis* Reiss, 1929; "Cotyplus" Isaszeg; 12c. male genitalia (uncus); 12d. lamina dorsalis (Fazekas 1982). The scales are different.

13. *Zygaena (Mesembrynus) cynarae* (Esper, 1789)

The sites for this species are mainly the sandy plains in the central part of the country, between the Danube and Tisza rivers. Unfortunately, breeding populations have not been observed in these sites for the last 50–60 years. The species has disappeared or become extinct in many places, such as the immediate vicinity of Budapest and the Mecsek Mountains in southern Hungary. It is important to note that it has also disappeared or become extinct from large areas of central Europe.

Bionomy: univoltine, from late May to early August. Primary foodplants of larvae: *Peucedanum cervaria*, *P. oreoselinum* and *Pimpinella major*. Secondary and occasional foodplants: *Peucedanum officinale*, *Pastinaca sativa* subsp. *pratensis*, *Libanotis pyrenaica*, *Daucus carota*. According to Varga (1969) the specimens from North Hungary (Zempléni Mountains; acid open rock grasslands) were bred on *Pimpinella major*. The food plants are different on the plains and in the mountain ranges. The primary food plant on the plain (e. g. closed loess and sand steppes) is *Peucedanum oreoselinum*, in the mountain ranges (e. g., rock- and slope steppes) *Peucedanum cervaria*.

Habitat: open sand steppes, calcareous open rock grasslands, acid open rocky grasslands, rocky steppes, slope steppes, closed loess, and sand steppes. Habitats are threatened by invasive weeds, overgrowth of shrubs and lack of mowing.

Remarks: According to Fazekas (1986; Abb. 1-8. and 9-25.): “About 250 specimens of this species from Hungary and neighbouring regions have been studied. The wing patterns of specimens belonging to the nominate subspecies and Hungarian specimens are illustrated to demonstrate the variation range. Parts of the male genitalia (uncus and lamina dorsalis) of specimens representing five different subspecies are figured. No differences in external appearance or in the genitalia could be found between specimens of the nominate subspecies and those from Hungarian populations. It is therefore concluded that the taxon *pusztae* Burgeff, 1926, is a synonym of nominotypical *Zygaena cynarae* Esper, 1789, and that Hungarian *cynarae* are referable to the nominate subspecies.”

13b ♂ A rare form (after genital examination)

13c Variability of the wing patch pattern

13d The species has disappeared or become extinct in many places, such as the Mecsek Mountains in southern Hungary (Pécs)

13e *Zygaena cynarae*: the variability of wing patterns (according to Fazekas 1986, Abb. 1–8, p. 279); 1–4. *Z. cynarae cynarae* (topotypes, Lwow | = Lemberg), 5–6. *Z. cynarae* var. *pusztiae* Burgeff, 1926; 7–8. *Z. cynarae* (Pomáz); scale bar= 10 mm.

13f Habitat of *Z. cynarae*: Kiskunság National Park (Peszéradacsi-rétek), UTM CT 61 (see black arrow)

14. *Zygaena (Mesembrynus) laeta* (Hübner, 1790)

This species is protected in Hungary; its incorporeal value is 100 000 HUF. Very local and rare. It has disappeared from many places: Mecsek Mountains, Somogy County, Lake Fertő region, Budapest, and its neighbourhood.

Bionomy: univoltine from July to August. The larvae feed on *Eryngium campestre*. The specimens from Kiskunság National Park (Kis-Nyír) were bred on *Pimpinella saxifraga*.

Habitat: A typical inhabitant of Pannonian steppe regions, occurring on dry, calcareous ground, open sand steppes, or on dry sheepfolds (e.g., Mezőföld region).

Remarks: A typical expansive Ponto-Mediterranean species in Hungary. Known only in some isolated populations between which gene flow is uncertain, although their survival is possible. The species seems to be in regression. Until the middle of the 20th Century it was a typical species of the sandy landscapes of central Hungary. Unfortunately, these habitats were planted with *Pinus sylvestris* and *Robinia pseudoacacia* and many old, natural habitats have been destroyed. This is now a rare and local species in its whole range. The majority of literature records report single specimens or lack data on the number of observed specimens. Most of the records before 1960 have not been confirmed.

14a ♂

14b Habitus pattern:
Keszthely, 04.07.2016
(© Ullén F.)
The locality is indicated by the
black arrow.

15. *Zygaena (Mesembrynus) brizae* (Esper, 1800)

The most significant Hungarian population of this species flourishes in the Northern mountain ranges of Hungary (e. g. Bükk Mountains, Aggtelek karst). In the past decades, the size of populations has reduced considerably, and therefore the survival of local populations can be ensured only protected areas.

Bionomy: univoltine from late May to July. Larval foodplants: *Cirsium eriophorum*, *C. arvense*, *C. pannonicum*, *Onopodum acanthium*. According to Varga (1969) primary foodplant in the North Hungary (e. g., Aggtelek National Park) is *Serratula tinctoria*.

Habitat: sunny meadows, most rarely on marsh meadows, on pastures and on rocky mountainsides.

Remarks: distribution and conservation status in Hungary: species known only in nature reserves. The type of locality of the nominotypical subspecies is in Hungary.

15b The forewings and hindwings are geographically variable. There are many specimens with a faded ground colour, greyish-black. The central stripe may be thinned, but sometimes resembles the *Zygaena purpuralis* species.

16. *Zygaena (Mesembrynus) minos* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Due to earlier taxonomic problems, the exact geographical distribution of *Z. minos/purpuralis* species-pair is only partially known. The moth is indistinguishable from *Z. purpuralis* in the field, only by genital dissection. The larvae, however, are easily distinguished. The author gives a detailed analysis of the differential features of the species-pair and has begun a complete revision of the Hungarian Collection (Fazekas 2002: 148 p.). Based on the specimens examined in detail, the geographic distribution in Hungary is as follows: most of the sites are west of the Danube River (Transdanubia). Most of the populations are highly isolated, with low numbers of individuals. In northern Hungary, it is documented in the Mátra and Bükk mountain ranges. Most of the Hungarian populations are in protected areas. Populations in the lowland areas (Danube-Tisza köze) should be reviewed.

Bionomy: univoltine from early June to mid-August. Larval foodplants: *Eryngium campestre*, *Falcaria vulgaris*, *Pimpinella saxifraga*.

Habitat: this widespread species is ecologically non-flexible; mainly on hills and in mountains of medium height; on dry meadows, on pastures and on waysides. Altitude from 90 m to 900 m.

Remarks: Distribution and conservation status in Hungary: determination of distribution frequency is uncertain due to incomplete research. Known only in local populations.

16a ♂

16b Different wing patterns; lighter and darker base colours and variable wing patches.

17. *Zygaena (Mesembrynus) purpuralis* (Brünnich, 1763)

Known mainly in the mountains, on the low hills, and locally on the plains. Distribution and conservation status in Hungary: locally distributed species which can occur in large numbers in favourable places.

Biology: univoltine, from late May to early August. Larva oligophagous: *Thymus pannonicus*, *T. praecox*, *T. serphyllum*.

Habitat: this widespread species is ecologically very flexible; rock and slope steppes, white oak scrub woodlands, sweet chestnut woodlands, on closed loess and sand steppes.

Remarks: There are no known specimens from near the Croatian and Romanian borders, but collectors and researchers have not yet investigated these areas.

17b The species is highly variable in Hungary. In some populations, suffused, confluent forms occur regularly. Variability is common especially in populations above 500–600 m.

17c Spot 1 is reduced.

18. *Zygaena (Agrumenia) fausta* (Linnaeus, 1767)

One of the rarest and most mysterious species of Zygaenidae in Hungary. European authors have ignored the Hungarian populations of *Z. fausta* until now. Breeding populations were discovered in four places between 1965 and 1979, although we have no recent data. The identification and collectors of the species are authentic, and voucher specimens are preserved in the Hungarian Museum of Natural Science (Fazekas 1989, 1995, 2009). Fazekas (1995) gives voucher specimens known from the Hungary as follows: “♂, West-Ungarn, Nagykanizsa 1889, leg. anon, GU Fazekas, Nr. 983; Százhalombatta bei Budapest, ♀ 08.08.1965 leg. Seregélyes T., GU Fazekas, Nr. 984; Százhalombatta, ♀, 08.08.1965, leg. Agócsy P., GU Fazekas, Nr. 1015; Budaer-Gebirge, Dobogókő, ♂, VI.29., leg. anon, GU Fazekas, Nr. 1014; Bakony-Gebirge, Öskü, 2 ♂, 19.07.1979 leg. et GU Fazekas.” Another specimen from a new site was found: Fót, Somlyó-hegy, 21.07.1979, leg. F. Buschmann, in coll. Jász Museum (Jászberény). The specimen is authentic. The author has written about the species in detail in a paper, including the habitus of the specimen (Buschmann 2012).

Bionomy: univoltine, from late June to mid-August. Larva monophagous. Possible food crops in Hungary: *Coronilla vaginalis* and *C. coronata*. The geographical distribution of these plant species in Hungary is consistent with known *Z. fausta* localities. Unfortunately, no larvae have been observed so far.

Habitat: A typical xerothermophil species, on closed rock grasslands and rock steppes.

Remarks: Distribution and conservation status in Hungary: populations have disappeared or presumably become extinct since 1965 and 1979. Gene flow is uncertain; the species can be in regression.

19. *Zygaena (Agrumenia) carniolica* (Scopoli, 1763)

Known on Hungary mainly on the hills and in mountains of medium height (Transdanubia, Northern Hungary), with limited distribution in Eastern Hungary. Distribution and conservation status in Hungary: a widespread and mostly frequent euryoecious species.

Bionomy: univoltine, from late May to mid-July. Larva oligophagous: *Anthyllis vulneraria*, *Dorycnium herbaceum*, *Onobrychis viciifolia*, *O. arenaria*, *Lotus pedunculatus*, *L. corniculatus*.

Habitat: this widespread species is ecologically very flexible; colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, halophytic habitats, dry open grasslands, closed rock grasslands, slope steppe, closed loess and sand steppes, white oak scrub woodlands, loess steppe oak woodlands, open sand steppe oak woodlands, arable land limited, often low-intensity agriculture.

Remarks: in the last 20–30 years, the number of sightings in south-western Hungary (e.g., Baranya county) has been steadily decreasing. In sites where it was common in the past, now only a few specimens can be seen. This is particularly noticeable in the Mecsek Mountains, especially where chemical mosquito eradication has been carried out. Not only have Zygaenid species disappeared, but all butterflies (Rhopalocera) too.

19a-e Wing pattern of the specimens sampled

19g

19g Spot types with distinct white to yellowish spot border of *Zygaena carniolica* specimens in Hungary

19h Morphometric. Landmarks on the of wings are numbered. Generalized *Zygaena carniolica* wing pattern from above. Spot type: 1+2, 3, 4, 5, 6.

The 6th spot is highly variable, sometimes breaking up into small patches. The white ring of spots 3, 4 and 5 may disappear.

20. *Zygaena (Zygaena) loti* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Widespread in Hungary mainly on the hills and in mountains of medium height (Transdanubia, Northern Hungary), with limited distribution in Eastern Hungary. Mostly frequent euryoecious species.

Bionomy: univoltine, from late May to mid-August. Larva oligophagous: *Coronilla varia*, *Dorycnium herbaceum*, *Hippocrepis glauca*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Trifolium alpestre*, *Onobrychis arenaria*. Behaviour: Normally occurs great profusion, feeding in particular at flowers of species of *Knautia*, *Scabiosa*, *Centaurea*, *Dianthus*, *Oryganum* and *Echium*.

Habitat: colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, dry open grasslands, dry and semi-dry closed grasslands, white oak scrub woodlands, open sand steppe, oak woodlands, poplar-juniper steppe woodlands, thermophilous woodland fringes, wooded pastures, sweet chestnut woodlands.

Remarks: The distribution map shows that it is very localised in the highly continental Hungarian lowlands. There are several reasons for this: 1) natural vegetation has disappeared, 2) almost all areas have been occupied by intensive agriculture, 3) only in National Park areas are there suitable habitats, 4) there has been very little planned collection in the lowland areas.

20a Variability of forewings patches

21. *Zygaena (Zygaena) osterodensis* H. Reiss, 1921

Rare and local in West Hungarian Borderland, in Transdanubian Mountains and in North Hungarian Mountains at altitudes between 200 m and 1000 m (Mátra Mts., Bükk Mts.). Absent or unrecorded from huge areas of the country. In the Great Plain, it has only been collected in the Jászság region (Buschmann 2012). It has disappeared from old habitats around Budapest. In the south-west, south of Lake Balaton, towards the Croatian border, only one site is known.

Bionomy: univoltine, from early of June to mid-August. In Hungary, the moths usually rest on and feed at the flowers of species of *Knautia*, *Lathyrus*, *Scabiosa*, *Vicia* and *Valeriana*. Larval foodplants: *Lathyrus sativus*, *L. pratensis*, *L. niger*, *L. vernus*, *Vicia tenuifolia*.

Habitat: *Z. osterodensis* is a meso- and semi hygrophilous species, mainly on hills and in mountains of medium height; *Arrhenatherum* hay meadows, *Festuca rubra* hay meadows and related communities, colline and montane wet degraded grasslands, woodland fringes. It also likes the forest lands. An unprecedented population was found in the Bakony Mountains, in Kab-Mount, in 2020. The habitat is a typical closed thermophilous *Quercus pubescens* forest. The moths were flying very early, already in the first week of May. The forested area is surrounded by calcareous rocky steppes and slope steppe on stony soils vegetation dominant.

Remarks: Distribution and conservation status in Hungary: species known only in nature reserves; gene flow is uncertain.

21c Typical habitat of *Z. osterodensis*; Bükk Mts., Nagymező, 730 m (© Gál M.)

21d Individual variation of *Z. osterodensis* is generally not significant, but many forms are present in the higher areas of the central mountains. It is mainly the 3+5 spot that separates, the 2+5 spot thins or splits into two.

21e The distribution map shows that *Zygaena osterodensis* is absent from lowland areas with a strongly continental climate. It mainly prefers the more humid hilly- and mountainous areas.

22. *Zygaena (Zygaena) viciae* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Widespread but local and may occur in larger numbers in wet habitats. Very local and little-known species in east Hungary (e.g., Maros–Körösköze, Nagykunság), and to the south, along the river Drava, directly on the Croatian border (Drávafok).

Bionomy: flight period from late May to late July. Larva oligophagous: *Medicago sativa*, *Trifolium campestre*, *T. repens*, *T. alpestre*, *T. medium*, *Dorycnium herbaceum*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Onobrychis viciifolia*, *Vicia cassubica*, *V. cracca*, *V. tenuifolia*, *Lathyrus pratensis*.

Habitat: colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths; local on rock steppes, slope steppes and closed loess and sand steppes.

Remarks: distribution and conservation status in Hungary: locally distributed species which can occur in greater numbers in favoured localities. The old data for the Budapest area should be reviewed. The revised specimens are kept in the Hungarian Natural History Museum. It is important to note that it was the dominant species in the southern part of the country (in Mecsek Mountains) in the 1970's and 1980's. In the last 1-2 decades, the abundance has decreased dramatically.

22b Rare 6-spotted forms in 5-spotted populations

23. *Zygaena (Zygaena) ephialtes* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Many specimens in museum and private collections were collected 50-60 years ago. The distribution map drawn from these locality data is very misleading, as the recent data show a strong regression. Most of the sites are known west of the Danube River. There is often a large distance between local habitats. Abundance is very low. In the North Hungarian mountains (e.g., Mátra Mts., Bükk Mts.) stronger populations occur in landscape protection areas, National Parks, and Natura 2000 sites. There are hardly any observations from the lowland region.

Biology: flight period from July to mid-August. According to Gozmány (1963) from mid-May to early August. It is possible that sometimes two generations occur. Larva oligophagous: *Coronilla varia*, *C. emerus*, *Hippocrepis comosa*, *Onobrychis vicifolia*, *Vicia cracca*. According to Gozmány (1963) the larva feeds on *Thymus*.

Habitat: colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths. Distribution and conservation status in Hungary: locally distributed but known only in nature reserves.

Remarks: In the last decade, several isolated populations have been found east of the Tisza River. These isolates are highly threatened, mainly due to intensive agricultural cultivation.

23a *Z. ephialtes f. coronillae*

23b *Z. ephialtes f. aeacus*

23c *Z. ephialtes f. peucedani*

23d *Z. ephialtes f. ephialtes*

23e *Z. ephialtes f. coronillae*; widespread in Hungary (© Gergely P.)

23f *Z. ephialtes f. peucedani*: the underside of the wings

23g Rare varieties of *Z. ephialtes* forma unknown from southern Hungary (Mecsek Mts.)

24. *Zygaena (Zygaena) angelicae* Ochseneimer, 1808

Hungarian populations live in the fluctuation zone of the species' distribution limit.

Z. angelicae is very local and rare in Hungary. Many habitats have been destroyed in the agglomeration of settlements. The survival of the species is mostly ensured in the northern North Hungarian mountains and in the Austrian-Hungarian border area. The situation in the lowlands is critical, with a lack of observations and surveys.

Bionomy: flight period from late June to late July. Larva oligophagous: *Lotus corniculatus*, *Coronilla emerus*, *C. varia*, *C. coronata*, *Hippocrepis comosa*.

Habitat: colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, closed rock grasslands, rock steppes, slope steppes.

Remarks: distribution and conservation status in Hungary: local and rare in mountains of moderate altitude, gene flow is uncertain. The species is likely to be in regression.

24a ♂

24a The underside of the wings (x 1,5 approx.)

25. *Zygaena (Zygaena) filipendulae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Widespread on the hills and in the mountains of medium altitude, very local on the plains.

Bionomy: flight period from late May to mid-August. The species normally occurs in great profusion, feeding preferably at the flowers of species of *Carduus*, *Centaurea*, *Knautia*, *Scabiosa*, *Origanum* and *Eupatorium*. Larva oligophagous on *Dorycnium herbaceum*, *Lotus pedunculatus*, *L. corniculatus*, *Coronilla emerus*, *C. coronata*, *Onobrychis viciifolia*, and *Lathyrus sylvestris*. According to Gozmány (1963), the larva feeds on *Trifolium* spp. In the Hungarian lowlands, east of the Tisza river (Kiskunmajsza, Kisújszállás), a very interesting observation was made by Kelemen et al. (2011). In 2010, in the month of September, when mating individuals were found (06.09.2010 and 26.09.2010). The moths were feeding on *Centaurea pannonica* flowers. In Hungary, such late flight times have never been recorded before.

Habitat: colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths.

Remarks: distribution and conservation status in Hungary: found everywhere, and a common species in most localities.

25a ♂

25b The underside of the wings
(x1,5 approx.)

26. *Zygaena (Zygaena) lonicerae* (Scheven, 1777)

Widespread on the hills and in the mountains of medium altitude, very local on the Hungarian plains. Most have been collected west of the Danube River, as far as the Austrian border. It is hardly known at present along the Slovenian and Croatian borders.

Bionomy: flight period from mid-May to mid-August. *Z. lonicerae* normally occurs great profusion, feeding preferably at the flowers of species of *Centaurea*, *Cirsium*, *Knautia* and *Scabiosa*. Larva oligophagous, on *Trifolium montanum*, *T. repens*, *T. alpestre*, *T. pannonicum*, *T. medium*, *Lotus pedunculatus*, *L. corniculatus*, *Astragalus onobrychis*, *Coronilla varia*, *Onobrychis viciifolia*, *Hippocrepis comosa*, *Vicia sylvatica*.

Habitat: mainly in hilly and mountainous meadows and pastures, sparse shrublands, forest edge zones, rocky hillsides, on roadsides. The moth present very locally in mown fields, pastures, or abandoned weedy areas near lowland rivers (e.g., Duna, Tisza, Körös).

Remarks: on the distribution map, it is very striking that in most of the country, in the lowlands, there are hardly any sites. However, the potential localities have not yet been systematically investigated. Especially near the Ukrainian and Romanian borders, habitats of the species should be sought.

26c Variability in wing pattern in Hungarian populations (original graphics by the author)

Questionable or incorrectly identified species from Hungary

Records of several Hungarian species are based on misidentification. Only one early specimen of *Zygaena trifolii* (Esper, 1783) is known. Recent research has not confirmed its presence and presumably, the specimen is wrongly labelled. Specimens of *Zygaena contaminei* Boisduval, 1834 from the Bükk National Park (North Hungarian Mts) and *Zygaena diaphana* Staudinger, 1887 have been misidentified (Ács & Szabóky 1993) and belong to other species. *Zygaena contaminei* is endemic to the Iberian Peninsula and does not occur in other parts of Europe.

According to Nahirnić (2019) *Z. diaphana* is a “bona species”. For a long time, the taxonomic status of the species was highly questionable. Its identification is exceedingly difficult as it occurs in the Balkans together with its sister species *Z. minos*. The exact geographic distribution of *Z. diaphana* is not yet known. Further in-depth research is needed to determine whether its area reaches Hungary.

The record of Hungarian *Adscita mannii* (Lederer, 1853) is also based on a misidentification. According to Ács & Szabóky (1993) known a species in the Bükk Mts (North Hungary): “*Adscita appendiculata* (Esper, [1777])”. Such taxon unknown in Hungary and in Palearctic region.

Z. trifolii (Spain)
(© Fernández-Rubio F.)

Z. contaminei (Spain)
(© Fernández-Rubio F.)

A. mannii (Croatia, Istria)
(© Fazekas I.)

A final note on the *Zygaena fausta* species: According to European Zyganidae specialists a native occurrence of this species in Hungary is doubtful. G. Tarmann (pers. comm.) believes that this species even could have been introduced to Hungary in historical times for some reason and has disappeared now. According to Tarmann know *Z. fausta* from other places in Europe where this species does not occur (e.g. a series of *Z. fausta* in the Rothschild collection in London from Austria, Leithagebirge). Biogeographically a western European distribution with a local and isolated sub-population in Hungary is most peculiar. May it be possible that someone has introduced this species into Hungary deliberately or that it came somehow by agricultural products in earlier times? Of course, we cannot prove anything nowadays.

According to Tarmann similar cases are known for *Adscita mannii* (Lederer, 1853) and *T. ampellophaga* in North Africa.

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